

**AN ANALYSIS OF THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN
SCHOOL MANAGER'S PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT CAPACITY
AND THE IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RESOURCE
DEVELOPMENT POLICY IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS
IN NYERI COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

School managers in Public primary schools in Kenya are required to implement the human resource policy through enhancement of continuous teachers' professional development. However, the implementation is shallow due to inadequacy in school management capacity. Profession development for teachers remains a key aspect of the human resource development policy. The aim of this study was to analyze the association between school manager's professional development capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools in Nyeri County. Two theories namely, the behavioral theory of management and the policy formulation and implementation theories were adopted to guide the study. Quantitative and qualitative data was collected using the survey and in-depth interviews methods respectively. The concurrent triangulation design was used throughout the data collection period and during the analysis of both the qualitative and quantitative data. The target population of the study consisted of four hundred (400) headteachers, one thousand six hundred (1600) teachers, four hundred (400) chairpersons of public primary schools board of management and eight (8) sub county TSC human resource officers. Stratified Random Sampling was applied to come up with a sample size of fifty (50) head teachers, one hundred and sixty (160) teachers and fifty (50) board of management chairpersons in public primary schools. All the Eight (8) Sub County TSC Human Resource Officers were purposively selected. The independent variable was school manager's professional development capacity while the dependent variable was the implementation of the human resource development policy in public

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primary schools. The questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from head teachers and teachers in the selected public primary schools. Interview schedules were used to collect qualitative data from chairpersons of the schools' board of management and from the sub county TSC human resource officers. Piloting of instruments was done prior to the final collecting of data to enhance validity. Credibility was enhanced through the adjustments of the tools according to the opinions given by respondents during the piloting phase and the guidance from supervisors. Interactive questioning was used to enhance dependability. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically. The Chi square was applied for analysis of inferential statistics using SPSS program version 24. Qualitative data was compared with quantitative data at the final analysis. The reporting of the quantitative data included percentages, tables and charts while qualitative data was by the Chi square values, inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that there is a conducive environment for teachers to work in. However, teachers are not regularly taken for seminars and workshops thereby hindering their professional development. The researcher recommended that headteachers of public primary schools should be properly trained on professional development of teachers. Additionally, the school managers should have a reduced workload and adequate finances to enable them to carry out the teacher's professional development role effectively.

Keywords: professional development, human resource development policy, Implementation

1. Introduction

Wanzare (2000) stated that professional upgrading should broaden and deepen knowledge of the content. It also gives a robust base for the means of specific knowledge and disciplines about the learning and teaching processes. Professional development arrangements have to be well rooted in and also portrays effective available research. The materials of professional development arrangements should be done accordance with the curriculum and standards used in the institution. It gives to quantifiable improvement in learners' attainment, engage and address intellectually the teaching complexity. It also gives adequate time, resource and support to make it possible for teachers to acquire and fully understand new pedagogy and content and to use the skills and knowledge to improve their work.

Professional upgrading should involve educators and other qualified personnel in the area and take various forms, site specific and job embedded. It is important for old educators to continue professional development and normal chances to learn from each other. Continuous professional upgrading enable educators to be up-to-date on recent research on learning, dynamic technology and its tools used in classes, modern curriculum resources among others. The effective professional development is continuous, collaborative, experiential, and networked to and sourced from working

together with learners and knowing their culture (Edutopia, 2008). Professional development is a continuous process. It acts as one of the core parts in managerial roles of headteachers' performance management. Continuous development depends on the supposition that upgrading the skills and ability of educators will enhance performance. Professionally upgraded educator is committed towards attaining the requirements of specific individual teacher. Teachers, who have undergone professional development, improve learning quality in learning setting. Such teachers are accountable for their actions and respect their colleagues, family, children and other experts in their working settings. Comprehensive professional upgrading arrangements for educators have to focus directly on student assistance in order to achieve the goal of learning. The ministry in charge of education in Kenya is responsible for educational policy formulation. However, the policy implementation is left to county directors and the school managers at regional level to interpret and implement.

2. Statement of the Problem

School managers have been reported to be lacking in important management capacity consequently hindering the implementation of human resource development policy in their respective schools. Professional development among teachers plays a critical role in ensuring productivity and effectiveness in their work. Lack of capacity to implement this aspect of the human resource development policy has greatly hindered the implementation of the human resource development policy. Global changes across the education sector require continuous professional upgrading of teachers. The researcher therefore sought to find out whether there was an association between school manager's professional development capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools in Nyeri County, Kenya.

2.1 Research Objective

The objective of the study was to analyze the association between school manager's professional development capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools.

2.2 Research Hypothesis

There is no association between school manager's professional development capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools.

2.3 Significance of the Study

The school managers may improve on teachers' assessment training needs and therefore initiate teachers' seminars and workshops geared towards improving their professional competence. The ministry of education may adapt the recommendations of this study which includes training of managerial skills to headteachers.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Teachers Professional Development and the Implementation of the Human Resource Development Policy

Hayes (2010) states that professional development refers to as all types of educational practices and experiences acquired by particular individual related to his/her specialization. The researcher further indicates that majority of employees are required to attend in-service learning as required by the profession, to secure their jobs. School systems currently are faced with task of addressing the increasing demands of teachers' development that adopting evidence-based habits and managing the needs. In addition, Speck (2005) indicates that professional development involves the learning to achieve or maintain professional knowledge's for instance academic degrees required for formal coursework, informal learning and conferences opportunities meant for practice.

Jacob (2002) stated that in the education sector, school leadership and teaching quality are critical factors for improving students' achievement. Therefore, to ensure efficiency in their teaching career, teachers should continuously increase their skills and knowledge for them to offer the best in teaching practices. Webb (2007) reveals that professional development should be clearly defined, appropriately sequenced that involves a variety of processes to adequately offer the much needed assistance to teachers in the constructing their own initial knowledge content from their own prior experiences to produce more competent teachers. These experiences need to be provided in an environment which is comfortable for teachers in practicing, exploring and experimenting with the contents and tools. The activities mentioned ought to produce quality results and also build professional associations that the experienced teachers should support and guide the less versed ones therefore enhancing collaborative learning among members. Professional upgrading is referred as a way of strengthening, sharpening and updating of employees' skills and creating an understanding and anxieties in various professional duties (Mohanty, 2003).

3.2 Research Methodology and Design

3.2.1 Research Methodology

The study adapted the survey method in collecting quantitative data while interviews were used in collecting qualitative data. According to Kerlinger (1973), Survey research is a study on large and small populations which involves selecting samples from the target population in order to find out interrelations.

3.2.2 Research Design

The concurrent triangulation design which allows analysis, interpretation and comparison of both qualitative and quantitative data was adapted in this study. This design is usually used when a direct comparison or contrast is needed in Quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings (Creswell, Plano Clark et.al 2003).

4. Research Findings and Recommendations

Table 1: School Manager's Professional Development Capacity and the Implementation of Human Resource Development Policy

Summary of Test Items	Headteachers					Teachers				
	SA	A	N	D	SD	SA	A	N	D	SD
	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
There is effective human resource training for human resource development in my school	7 16	1 2	4 9	14 31	19 42	27 18	22 15	23 16	36 24	40 27
Teachers are regularly taken for bench markings by school management to improve teaching skills	4 9	11 24	5 11	16 36	9 20	25 17	25 17	25 17	48 32	24 16
Training need assessment is regularly conducted in my school for enhancing human resource development	1 2	7 16	7 16	19 42	11 24	13 9	1 1	13 9	61 41	60 40
School managers have been a role model to teachers in enhancing human resource development in my school	15 33	15 33	7 16	6 13	2 4	54 36	30 20	13 9	25 17	25 17
Professional counselling of teachers is normally conducted in my school for human resource development	1 2	6 13	8 18	19 42	11 24	15 10	31 21	10 7	37 25	55 37

Table 1 indicates that an impressive majority of the headteachers 19(42%) disagreed that there is effective human resource training for human resource development in the school and a further 14(31%) strongly disagreed. However, 4(9%) were neutral and 7(16%) strongly agreed whereas only 1(2%) agreed. Further, a fair number of the teachers who responded 40(27%) strongly disagreed that there is effective human resource training for human resource development, 36(24%) disagreed while 23(16%) remained neutral. Further, 27(18%) strongly agreed whereas only 22(15%) agreed.

According to the data on table 1 above a majority of sampled headteachers 16(36%) disagreed with the opinion that training need assessment is regularly conducted in their school for enhancing human resource development by school management in order to improve teaching skills as did a further 9(20%) who strongly disagreed. At the same time 11(24%) agreed, a few 4(9%) strongly agreed while 5(11%) chose to remain neutral. On the other hand, 48(32%) of sampled teachers responded by disagreeing, a further 24(16%) strongly disagreed while 25(17%) strongly agreed, 25(17%) agreed and a similar number 25(17%) remained neutral.

The data on table 1 reveals that the majority, 15(33%) of the headteachers strongly agreed and a similar number 15(33%) agreed that school managers have been a role model to enhance human resource development in my school. However, 7(16%) were neutral, 6(13%) disagreed while only 2(4%) strongly disagreed. On the other hand teachers shared very similar sentiments with a large number 54(36%) strongly agreeing and a further 30(20%) who agreed that there was positive change by school human

resource after undergoing human resource development. At the same time 2(17%) disagreed and a similar number 26(17%) strongly disagreed while 13(9%) remained neutral.

Further findings, revealed that headteachers 19(42%) disagreed that professional counselling of teachers is normally conducted in school for human resource development, 11(24%) strongly disagreed. Only 1(2%) of headteachers who strongly agreed, a further 6(13%) agreed while 8(18%) were neutral. At the same time 55(37%) of teachers strongly disagreed that disagreed that professional counselling of teachers is normally conducted in school for human resource development and supported by a further 37(25%) who disagreed. However, 31(21%) agreed while 15(10%) strongly agreed. Those who remained neutral were 10(7%). In the same view staff training and development enhances teachers with new teaching skills and methodologies required for performing other duties and for effective teaching. For teachers are implementers of education curriculums, they translate policy statements and aim into real outcomes and activities in classroom. Barasa (2005) stated that in-service courses that are meant for staff development can be implemented in various ways such as re-orienting teachers, improving their academic grades and expanding teachers' capabilities. It is through these new capabilities that will make teaching staffs to effectively perform their roles in changing education systems.

Table 2: Chi Tests for Association between School Manager's Professional Development Capacity and the Implementation of Human Resource Development Policy

	Headteachers			Teachers		
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.520a	16	.101	.290a	16	.017
Likelihood Ratio	.430	16	.163	.576	16	.126
N of Valid Cases	45			149		

*. Association is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Association is significant at the 0.00 level (2-tailed).

From Table 2, the findings between school management professional development capacity and implementation of human resource development policy are presented in form of a matrix such that the associations are replicated. A Chi square test was run to determine the association between school managers' teachers' professional development capacity and implementation of human resource development policy. The test found no association where $\chi^2 = .520$ and $.290$ chi values with corresponding significance of $p = .101$, and $p = .017$, which is greater than pre-determined value of $< .005$ thus indicating there was no statistical significance association. The study results were $p = .101$, $> .005$ by headteachers and $p = .017$, $> .005$ by teachers. The hypothesis H_{01} that stated that there is no association between school managers' professional development and implementation of human resource development policy was therefore accepted. These results confirms those of Esia & Ofosu (2014) who found that there is no

association between the effects of supervision of educational processes and their upgrading of their careers based on the behaviors of learners they teach. The researcher obtained $\chi^2 = 106$, $p = 7.81$. Ogembo (2005) stated that the appointment of school headteachers is usually done on a basis that pre-service professional training of headteachers together with the experience that they have acquired during teaching.

It is quite challenging to manage people working in certain institutions. Chemtai (2010) established that people or institution employees are vital assets in an institution and therefore it is imperative for the management to utilize them efficiently and effectively in order for the institutions to achieve the desired results. School managers are faced with management challenges especially when dealing with human resource policies. Development of human resource is a continuous activity and therefore there are always chances for improvement. Human resource development comes with challenges that call for coping measures to be enacted. School managers must take advantage of slow although profound changes affecting current practices, overall management policies affecting human resource, vision and mission of the institution. Ogunsaju (2006) posits that management of personnel can be termed as effective human resource mobilization that can be grounded on training, selection; recruitment and placement for institutions to achieve set objectives and goals. According to Stone (2006), the personnel management or the personnel administrator is an activity of managing people with few associations between organization activities and various activities.

Headteachers disagreed that there is effective human resource training for human resource development in the school. Further, both the headteachers and the teachers disagreed with the opinion that training need assessment is regularly conducted in the public primary school for enhancement of human resource development. While headteachers were found to have been role models to the teachers in professional development, lack of proper training and adequate time were cited as some of the challenges facing the implementation of the human resource development policy in the selected public primary schools. The researcher established that professional counselling of teachers as part of the implementation of the human resource development policy is rarely conducted in schools.

The duty of the school head is to ensure there is transparent and efficient management structure in their respective schools. Data was also collected from interview amongst the board of management chairpersons and Sub County Human Resource officers on teachers' professional development capacity and the implementation of human resource. During the interview, most BOM chairpersons and SHRO indicated having teachers' professional development enables implementation of human resource in various ways. For instance, *"teachers' continuous learning enables staff awareness on emerging issues and act as expert delivery initiatives and thus the implementation of human resource policy is achieved"*. Most interviewees indicated that continuous learning of teachers creates awareness campaigns in teaching careers. Workshops and expert delivery campaigns are quite essential and necessary for the implementation of human resource policy. Most BOM chairpersons and SHRO stated that teachers'

continuous learning enable staff awareness on emerging issues and act as expert delivery initiatives and thus the implementation of human resource policy is achieved. Interviewees remarked that *"There is positive change after teachers attend seminars that can be seen in their ability to manage teaching and materials and in adopting new teaching skills to tackle challenging issues during teaching and learning processes."* This indicates that comprehensive teacher's development deepens teaching staffs' pedagogical and knowledge skills and also provides chances for research, reflection and practice that includes, collaborative, efforts on job-embedded and sustained and enables achieving of goals that remain updated.

The researcher recommended that the headteachers be properly trained on ways of handling professional development issues among teachers in order enhance the implementation of the human resource policy in their schools. The school managers were also found to be having limited time to effectively carry out and influence professional development for the teachers despite is cited as role models in the profession. Assigning headteachers lighter teaching load was highlighted as one of the ways of freeing up their time which is critical in the implementation of the human resource development policy.

References

1. Barasa, J. M. (2007). *Education Organization and Management*. Nairobi: Jomo Kenyatta Foundation.
2. Chemutai, C. (2010). *Impact of in-service training to head teachers on management of human resources in public secondary schools, Nandi-South District, Kenya*.(Unpublished Thesis) Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
3. Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. (2nd ed). Thousand Oaks, London: Sage.
4. Jacob, M., Clifford, P., & Friesen, S. (2002). *Preparing teachers for technology integration: Creating a culture of inquiry in the context of use*. Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education, 2(3), 363-388. Retrieved October 20, 2006, from <http://www.citejournal.org/vol2/iss3/currentpractice/currentpracticearticle2.pdf>
5. Kerlinger, F. (1973). *The structure of scientific revolution*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
6. Kumar, R. (2005). *Research methodology*. SAGE Publications.
7. Ogunsaju P. (2006). Human Capital Management for Effective Corporate Governance. Paper presented at a Workshop titled: *Corporate Governance for Sustainable National Development, April 2006*.
8. Wanzare, Z., O. (2002). Rethinking teacher evaluation in the third world: The case of Kenya. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 30, 213 – 229.

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